

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF PHOTOELECTRIC CONVERTERS WHEN CONNECTED IN SERIES

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***Annotation.** This is due to the fact that it is one of the most promising and environmentally friendly sectors of renewable energy my electric power industry. In addition, the modular design of photovoltaic installations allows them to be designed for almost any power, which makes these installations a versatile and reliable solution that is widely used in both industrial power generation and small power supply systems. The article discusses the features of the operation of photoelectric converters when connected in series under conditions of uniform and uneven illumination. The reasons for the decrease in energy efficiency in the case of partial shading are described.*

***Key words:** photovoltaic, serial connection, shading, efficiency improvement.*

Solar energy is currently becoming more widespread in the Russian Federation and in the world. This is due to the fact that it is one of the most promising and environmentally friendly branches of renewable electric power industry. In addition, the modular construction of photovoltaic systems allows them to be designed for almost any power, which makes these installations to be universal and reliable solution that is widely used both in industrial power generation and in small power supply systems. The article presents features of photoelectric converters operation at consecutive connection under conditions of uniform and not uniform illumination. The reasons of the energy efficiency reduction in case of partial shading are described. There is presented the research of the operation

of photoelectric converters with shunt diodes and their inefficiency in a number of cases on the example of the Sevastopol solar power plant and in combination with flat solar concentrators. There is described the operation of photoelectric converters using matching converters that makes it possible to provide more complete electrical energy take off under conditions of uneven illumination. The results of experimental researches are presented.

Advantages and disadvantages of technologies Solar power plant :

1. noiselessness of work;
2. the service life of solar cells is practically unlimited and can be tens of years;
3. the conversion of solar energy occurs mainly through the use of photovoltaic cells;
4. additional or autonomous source of electricity in a private house;
5. the possibility of obtaining a "green" tariff.

Disadvantages of ses technology:

6. dependence on the climatic characteristics of the area;
7. need for a large area.

Wps technology advantages:

8. wind energy is inexhaustible; the production of electricity using wind farms is not accompanied by hazardous emissions into the atmosphere;
9. the possibility of placement in hard-to-reach places;

- 10.require a small area and fit into any landscape; obtaining free electricity in the long term, no costs for fuel and its delivery;
- 11.autonomy - independence from the state and operation of external electrical networks.

Disadvantages of wes:

- 12.noise;
- 13.high price;
- 14.long payback period;
- 15.volatility and unregulated wind flow.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

In recent years, in many countries of the world, scientists have paid close attention to the development of power plants that use environmentally friendly "green" energy. And the most powerful and most accessible source of alternative energy is the Sun. Scientific developments and modern technologies have reached a high level. Solar energy is currently used to provide power to artificial space objects, satellites and manned space stations in Earth orbit, interplanetary research probes. And this is not the limit. Thanks to innovative technologies, the emergence of new materials, it has become possible to build solar power plants that are designed for autonomous power supply.

Figure 1 - Volt-ampere characteristics of normally lit In (U_n), shaded group of solar cells Iz (U_z) and a battery consisting of these groups I (U)

1 – normally illuminated panel; 2 - terminals; 3 - connecting wires; 4 - shaded panel

Figure 2 - Shading of photovoltaic panels at the Sevastopol solar power plants and switching panels into a battery.

Figure 3 .Volt-ampere characteristic of a solar cell battery with partial shading and shunt diodes.

III. CONCLUSION.

With all these advantages, there are also disadvantages of solar energy, which are quite easily solved:

Figure 4. Photovoltaic installation with a flat solar concentrator

This is due to the fact that it is one of the most promising and environmentally friendly sectors of renewable energy. In addition, the modular design of photovoltaic installations allows them to can be designed for almost any power, which makes these units a versatile and reliable solution that is widely used both in industrial power generation and in small power supply systems

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